

Electrochemical behavior of mixed complexes of terbium(III) with 4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol and 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol

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The polarographic behavior of Tb^{III} in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} KCl with PAR and PAN azo dyes has been investigated on a dme. Tb^{III} forms 1 : 1 complex with both the ligands at $\text{pH } 3.10 \pm 0.1$. Lingane's treatment is applied to calculate the formation constants of complexes $\log \beta_1$ for $[Tb(PAN)]^{3+}$ and $[Tb(PAR)]^{3+}$. Schapp and McMaster's polarographic method has been used to evaluate the stoichiometry and formation constant $\log \beta_{11}$ for the mixed ligand complex $[Tb(PAR)(PAN)]^{3+}$.

4-(2-Pyridylazo)resorcinol (PAR) and 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN) are known to form chelates with metal ions¹. Most of the studies on formation of mixed ligand complexes are directed towards elucidation of affinity of secondary ligands for the primary complexes of metals with multidentate ligands.

The present paper deals with the study of ternary complexes of Tb^{III} with PAR and PAN on a dropping mercury electrode surface.

Results and Discussion

Tb^{III} gives a well-defined reversible reduction wave in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} KCl plus 0.01% gelatin at $\text{pH } 3.10 \pm 0.1$.

Reduction of Tb^{III} and its complexes with the two ligands was also found to be of diffusion-controlled nature as the plots of i vs \sqrt{h} (effective height of mercury column) yielded straight-line passing through the origin. An analysis of the plots of $-E_{de}$ vs $\log i/(i_d-i)$ and $E_{3/4}-E_{1/4}$ values for the simple Tb^{III} and for its complexes with all the two ligands (azo dyes) revealed a reversible nature of reduction waves.

Effect of ligand concentration :

At $\text{pH } 3.10 \pm 0.1$, the half-wave potential of Tb^{III} shifted to lesser negative value on increasing the concentration of ligands. A Lingane³ treatment of the data revealed the formation of 1 : 1 complexes of Tb^{III} with both PAR and PAN. Stability constants of the complexes ($\log \beta_1$) for $[Tb(PAN)]^{3+}$ and $[Tb(PAR)]^{3+}$ was calculated to be 4.27 and 4.38, respectively. It is clear from the data that metal-ligand formation constants follow the order : Tb^{III} -PAN < Tb^{III} -PAR, which is in agreement with that reported in the literature³.

It may be stated here that in the present observation,

lower pH, i.e. 3.10 ± 0.1 , has been preferred because at this pH a soluble 1 : 1 metal : azo dye complex is formed which could be easily studied using polarographic method. However, at higher pH values of ≈ 6.5 and higher concentration of the reagents, precipitation takes place on standing.

Mixed complex of Tb^{III} (PAR) (PAN) :

In this study, the concentration of 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol, a weaker ligand, was kept constant at 0.1 mmol dm^{-3} and that of 4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol, a stronger ligand was varied from 0.001 to 0.1 mmol dm^{-3} . The $E_{1/2}$ values were found to be shifted to less negative values as compared to those obtained in the absence of 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol, thereby showing the formation of mixed complexes.

The polarographic characteristics and $F_{1/2}(XY)$ functions of mixed complexes of Tb^{III} with PAR and PAN are depicted in Table 1. The method of Schapp and McMasters² was used to evaluate the stoichiometry and the value of the formation constant of the ternary complex and the latter was found to be 7.5.

The mixing constant K_m (equilibrium constant) for the reaction,

is a measure of relative stability of mixed complexes in solution as compared to binary complexes calculated by the following equation⁴,

$$K_m = \beta_{11}/\sqrt{\beta_{10}\beta_{01}}$$

In the present case the value of $\log K_m$ comes out to be 3.0. Positive value of log of mixing constant shows that the mixed complex is more stable than the simple binary complex.

Table 1. Polarographic characteristics and $F_{ij}(XY)$ functions for Tb^{III} -1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol-4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol mixed system

$-E_{1/2}$ for metal ion = -1.78 V vs SCE, ionic strength = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (KCl), i_d metal ion = 14 div, Fixed [PAN] = 1 mmol dm⁻³, temp. = 25°

[PAR] mmol dm ⁻³	i_d (div)	$-E_{1/2}$ V vs SCE	$\Delta E_{1/2}$	$\log \frac{im}{ic}$	F_{00xy}	$F_{01(xy)}$ 10 ⁴	$F_{02(xy)}$ 10 ⁸
0.01	14.0	1.780					
0.02	11.0	1.750	0.03	0.1004			
0.06	9.0	1.738	0.042	0.1903			
0.08	5.0	1.726	0.054	0.4472	43		
0.11	3.5	1.705	0.075	0.6021	178	125	
0.12	3.3	1.701	0.079	0.6274	229	157	22
0.16	3.1	1.694	0.086	0.6542	351	194	40
0.18	3.0	1.691	0.089	0.6628	416	208	43
0.20	2.7	1.690	0.090	0.7143	547	253	61
0.24	2.5	1.688	0.092	0.7482	801	317	78
0.26	2.1	1.682	0.098	0.8195	955	351	85

$A = 40$. $B = 10000$.

The stabilization constants is given by the expression,

$$\log K_s = \log K_m - \log 2$$

In the present study the values of $\log K_s$ was calculated to be 2.7, a measure of stability of mixed complex.

Experimental

Stock solutions (0.01 mol dm⁻³) of PAR (B.D.H.) was prepared in CO₂ free double-distilled water and PAN (B.D.H.) in 80 : 20 ethanol : water medium. Tb^{III} solution (0.01 mol dm⁻³) was prepared by dissolving the metal oxide in minimum amount of conc. HCl (AnalaR), then heated to dryness and residue extracted in double-distilled water, and the solution was standardized by EDTA method⁵. KCl solution (1 mol dm⁻³) was prepared in double-distilled water and gelatin solution (0.1%) in hot distilled water.

A preliminary experimental set was prepared to study binary systems prior to the study of ternary systems by keeping overall concentration of KCl, gelatin and Tb^{III} fixed at 0.1 mol dm⁻³, 0.01% and 1 mmol dm⁻³, respectively. In the other sets, in addition to the above metal ion, supporting electrolyte and gelatin concentration, the ligand concentrations was varied from 0.001 to 1 mmol dm⁻³. For the study of ternary systems, concentration of the weaker ligand was fixed and that of the stronger ligand was varied.

HCl and NaOH solutions were used to adjust the pH value of test solutions to 3.10 ± 0.1. A Systronics LI-335 pH meter was used. Current-voltage curves were recorded on an Elico CL-357 polarograph. The capillary used had the characteristics : m , 2.15 mg/s, drop time, 3.1 s at 45 cm of effective height of mercury ($m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.15 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$). Dissolved oxygen was removed by passing purified nitrogen gas through the test solution for ~15 min before recording the polarogram.

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